

ReBioCycle in a nutshell

ReBioCycle provides a portfolio of advanced bio-plastic sorting and recycling technologies for bio-based biodegradable plastics within **three complementary waste-processor-centric hubs** at a demonstration scale located in **Italy, Spain, and the Netherlands**.

The Hubs

These hubs operate in real-world environments to efficiently recycle three types of bioplastics: PLA, PHA, and composites. The Hubs will provide **Real-World Demonstrations** and showcase our novel recycling solutions.

Project coordinator

University College Dublin,
BiOrbic Bioeconomy SFI
Research Centre
Kevin O'Connor

Project duration

4 years
1 October 2024 –
30 September 2028

Visit our website
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Media channels:

www.rebiocycle.eu

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ReBioCycle

A new European blueprint for circular bioplastics upcycling solutions

HUB Leader: **AIMPLAS**
PLASTICS TECHNOLOGY CENTRE

"The overall concept of the project is quite innovative, but one of the most innovative developments is the enzymatic recycling, where pretreatments and enzymes are going to be used to depolymerize bioplastics and then the monomers will serve as substrate to produce again PHAs."

**Pablo Ferrero Aguar, AIMPLAS
Biotechnology Group Leader**

Partners

 ES HUB Material Flow Overview

📍 Spain and Ireland

The Spanish hub will focus on enzymatic recycling technology, upscaling it to TRL 6. AIMPLAS leads the Spanish Hub. The microbial recycling technology will be brought to TRL 7 with expected resulting outcomes of up to 100kg rPHA. The mechanical recycling technology will be up-scaled to TRL 7 and will achieve 250 kg of rPLA and 250kg of rPHA.

The partners involved in this hub are AIMPLAS, Trinity College Dublin, GlasPort Bio, University of Galway O' Flaherty Lab, CSIC CIB Biological Research Center and TotalEnergies Corbion.

The hub activities will be implemented in the waste sorting site of Manises (Valencia, Spain) run by the S.A. Agricultores de la Vega de Valencia. Kaneka Belgium is also supporting this hub with the provision of PHA.

Input:

Sorting of mixed plastics from municipal solid waste.

Processes:

Enzymatic (microbial) and mechanical recycling.

Outputs Available:

rPHA and rPLA.

ES HUB Map

